

BADC Datasets and Services

May 2005

The screenshot shows the homepage of the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC). At the top, there is a navigation bar with tabs for Home, My BADC, Data, Search, Community, and Help. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with links for About the BADC, Login, New User Registration, and Apply for datasets. The main content area features a blue background with the BADC logo (a globe) on the left and a colorful atmospheric data visualization on the right. The text reads: "BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE". Below this, a paragraph describes the BADC's role as the NERC Designated Data Centre for Atmospheric Sciences. A "Latest News" section includes a link to "SAGE II version 6.2 data now available from BADC." and another link for "Other News". At the bottom, there is a logo for "NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science" and a footer with links for Home, Contact, and Disclaimer, along with the text "Last Modified: 03/04/2005 18:43:14".

Home My BADC Data Search Community Help

About the BADC Login New User Registration Apply for datasets

The British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) is the Natural Environment Research Council's (NERC) Designated Data Centre for the Atmospheric Sciences. The role of the BADC is to assist UK atmospheric researchers to locate, access and interpret atmospheric data and to ensure the long-term integrity of atmospheric data produced by NERC projects.

To find out more about the BADC, please follow the links on the sub-tab sections above.

Latest News: [SAGE II version 6.2 data now available from BADC.](#) [Other News](#)

 NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Home Contact Disclaimer Last Modified: 03/04/2005 18:43:14

<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk>

Index – 120 Datasets

Online	CD Rom	VHS Video	Remote	Authorisation required

The NCAS British Atmospheric Data Centre, May 2005

**NERC Centres for
Atmospheric Science**
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

NATURAL
ENVIRONMENT
RESEARCH COUNCIL

	Start date: 27-aug-2004 End date: 06-sep-2004	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/adriex/	
	Start date: 10-Sep-1982 End date: 21-May-2002	
	http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/	
	Start date: 12-aug-1987 End date: 04- oct-1987	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/aaoe/	
	Start date: 29-dec-1988 End date: 22-feb-1989	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/aase/	
	Start date: 01-oct-1991 End date: 31-mar-1992	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/aase2/	
	Start date: 21-jan-1994 End date: 04-nov-1994	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ashoe/	
	Start date: 01-aug-1991 End date: 31-jul-1995	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/atSr/	
	Start date: 08-Apr-1995 End date: 16-Oct-2001	
	http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/	
	Start date: 10-Sep-1982 End date: 01-Jan-1993	
	http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/	
	Start date: 01-jan-1998 End date: 31-dec-2003	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/nerc_assim_prog/	
	Start date: 02-apr-1996 End date: 30-dec-1998	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/acsoe/	
	Start date: 01-Jul-1995 End date: 31-Jan-2001	
	http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/cryostat/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/erbe/	
	Start date: 01-jan-1979 End date: 28-feb-1994	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ecmwf-era/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ecmwf-e40/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ecmwf-op/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ecmwf-trj/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/aam/	
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	Start date: 22-jul-2002 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/mipas/index.html	
	Start date: 01-feb-2004 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/sciamachy/index.html	
	Start date: 14-sep-2004 End date: 18-sep-2004	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/eaquate/	
	Start date: 15-nov-1991 End date: 30-apr-1992	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/easoe/	

	European eXport of Precursors and Ozone by long-Range Transport (EXPORT)	
	Start date: 01-aug-2000 End date: 31-aug-2000 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/export	
	Start date: 01-apr-1999 End date: 31-aug-2000 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/esa-wv	
	Start date: 09-mar-2004 End date: Not defined http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/faam/	
	Start date: Not defined End date: Not defined http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/firetracc/	
	Start date: Not defined End date: Not defined http://ggsps.rl.ac.uk/	
	Start date: 01-jan-1851 End date: 31-dec-1995 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/gosta/	
	Start date: 24-mar-1998 End date: 15-mar-1999 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/gome	
	Start date: 01-jan-1995 End date: 31-dec-2001 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/grape/	
	Start date: 01-jan-1738 End date: 31-mar-1992 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/gedex/	
	Start date: Not defined End date: Not defined http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hadcm3-control	
	Start date: 11-oct-1991 End date: Not defined http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/haloe/	
	Start date: 11-oct-1991 End date: 21-dec-2000 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/haloel3/	

	Start date: 01-jan-2004 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hirdls	
	Start date: 01-may-1993 End date: 30-apr-2000	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/hyrex/	
FAAM	Ice Nuclearisation in Wave Clouds (NU-WAVE)	
	Start date: 17-nov-2004 End date: 24-nov-2004	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/nu-wave/	
	Start date: 01-mar-2003 End date: 31-dec-2003	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isb52	
	Start date: 28-sep-1991 End date: 29-jul-1992	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isams/	
	Start date: 28-sep-1991 End date: 29-jul-1992	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isamsl3/	
	Start date: 01-jul-1983 End date: 30-sep-2001	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isccp_top	
	Start date: 01-jul-1983 End date: 31-dec-1999	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isccp_d1	
	Start date: 01-jul-1983 End date: 31-dec-1999	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isccp_d2	
	Start date: 01-jul-1983 End date: 31-dec-1990	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/isccp/	
	Start date: 01-jan-1987 End date: 31-dec-1988	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/islscp/	
	Start date: 12-jul-2004 End date: 03-aug-2004	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/itop/	

	Start date: 01-jan-1659 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/cet/	
	Start date: 07-jun-1999 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ukmo-charts	
	Start date: 01-jan-1945 End date: 31-dec-2004	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/height/	
	Start date: 01-jan-1873 End date: 31-dec-2004	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/mslp/	
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	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/surface/	
	Start date: 01-may-2004 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/um	
	Start date: 17-may-1993 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/mrf	
	Start date: 25-nov-1998 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/ukmo-wind-prof	
	Start date: 11-nov-1999 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/meteosat/	
	Start date: 14-feb-2004 End date: Not defined	
	http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/data/msg	

Collaborative workspaces

[ADRIEX](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[CEH-IDMS](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[CHABLIS](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[COAPEC](#) - invited members only.

[CRYOSTAT](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[CSIP](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[EAQUATE](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[Earth Simulator](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[EcoGrid](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[GRAPE](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[HIGEM](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[HIRDLS](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[ICARTT](#) (International Consortium for Atmospheric Research on Transport and Transformation) - invited members only. No public access.

[IPCC WGII AR4](#) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Working group II: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability) - invited members only. No public access.

[LINK Project](#) - Members access Public read-only access

[NAMBLEX](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[NERC Centres of Atmospheric Science \(NCAS\)](#) - invited members only. No public access. This is a new workspace on our new server machine. A read-only copy of the Original NCAS workspace is still available

[NERC DMAG](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[NERC e-science](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[Polluted Troposphere](#) - invited members only. No public access.

[RAPID Data centre administration](#) - invited members only. No public access.

What are collaborative workspaces?

The collaborative workspaces at the BADC use a software system called BSCW (*Basic Support for Cooperative Work*). This allows members to share documents and URLs, have discussions, contact other members of the workspace and maintain a group calendar.

Members can also be notified by e-mail when new items have been posted in the workspace, either via a 'daily report' or an immediate message.

How do I become a member of a workspace?

In order to become a workspace member you first need to be a registered BADC user. Once you have done that, please contact BADC support to request membership of a workspace. We will confirm your eligibility with the owner of the workspace before giving you access.

Can I start a new workspace?

If you would like a workspace for a topic related to Atmospheric Data then please contact us and we will be pleased to help you.

BADC Services

[News](#)

Recent news and Past News items

[Conferences](#)

Seminar lists and conference announcements

[Meeting Registration](#)

Do you need an online meeting registration system? We may be able to help!

[Meeting Date Organiser](#)

A simple tool for selecting the best date for a meeting by inviting participants to indicate their availability

[BADC Links Collection](#)

Extensive collection of WWW links relevant to atmospheric science

[Mailing lists](#)

If your project needs a mailing list we may be able to help

[Project Spaces](#)

Restricted FTP access to disk space dedicated to a specific project

[Who's who](#)

Find out who our users are, what research they are doing, what institutes they are from and more!

[Trajectory Service](#)

Service providing a user-friendly interface to an atmospheric trajectory model

Contact the BADC

When you contact BADC Support, your query will be directed to the appropriate person.

We store and review all queries received to help us improve our service. To keep track of your query we use specialist software which, amongst other things, will provide you with a complete history of all messages related to your query.

All queries receive feedback within 5 working days.

Email address: BADC@rl.ac.uk

Telephone/Voicemail: +44 (0) 1235 44 64 32

Fax: +44 (0) 1235 44 63 14

Postal address:

The British Atmospheric Data Centre,
Space Science and Technology Department
R25 - Room 2.119/120
CCLRC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton, nr Didcot
Oxfordshire
OX11 0QX
England, UK.

These details are also available via WAP phone at
<http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/index.wml>